

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

THE EFFECT OF THE USE OF ORGANIC-MINERAL FERTILIZERS AND GROWTH STIMULANTS ON THE GROWTH, DEVELOPMENT, PASSAGE OF PHENOLOGICAL STAGES AND POTATO YIELD IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE FOOTHILL ZONE

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Abstract

The article presents the results of three-year studies on the growth, development, transition of phenological stages and changes in yield of cultivated potatoes under the conditions of the Askeran region of the Republic of Artsakh under the influence of separate and joint application of organo-mineral fertilizers and growth promoters. According to the research results, it was found that the fractional application of organomix and mineral fertilizers (in sowing and nutrition) and their joint equivalent doses in comparison to the one-time application (only in sowing), had a more positive effect on potato growth, development and transition of phenophases, contributing to high potato yields. Compared to the variant without fertilization, in the case of a one-time application of fertilizers, the yield increase was 146.8-150.3 c/ha or 101.3-104.1%, and their fractional equivalent doses were 158.1-167.8 c/ha or 109.1-115.8% increase in potato yield.

At the same time, the studies revealed that by changing the method of application of bioliquid as a growth stimulator, by soaking the seeds before planting, compared to foliar feeding, the increase in potato yield was 44.0 c/ha or 30.4%.

Keywords: organic-mineral fertilizers, growth stimulant, potato, phenological observations and biometric measurements, yield.

Modernity: In the life of plants and animals, in inanimate nature, there are many phenomena that are closely related to the successive changes of the seasons and are seasonal in nature. A special science, phenology, deals with the study of patterns of changes in such phenomena. The purpose of phenology is to highlight the development patterns of seasonal phenomena, as well as the changes occurring under the influence of this or that factor, to find the patterns caused by these changes and to make the phenomena caused by the given factor manageable with them [5,11]. One of the main goals of phenologists is also to help specialists in the field of agriculture and other fields to find the right solution to the issues raised. For example, during the period of spring work, farmers are primarily interested in the sowing dates of various crops, which can be determined with approximate accuracy with the help of phen indicators obtained on the basis of observations made over many years. Thus, phenological observations have shown that the planting of potatoes coincides with the flowering of dandelions, and the best time for sowing corn coincides with cherry

blossom. Or, observations made on the ripening process of agricultural crops allow to determine the best dates for harvesting and to take measures to harvest the crop without loss. The peculiarity of the nature of mountainous regions is that the sequence of phenomena is observed according to vertical zonation. The analysis of the phenological data of many agricultural crops and wild plant species showed that for every 100m of elevation, plant development is delayed by an average of 3-5 days in spring, and in autumn it is relatively fast, only in the opposite direction, the periods are delayed from top to bottom [10]. It has also been found that the same plant grown at the same height above sea level, but in different regions, goes through one or another stage of its development at the same time. It is due to many reasons: the position of the slopes, soil moisture, the degree of nutrient availability, varietal characteristics, etc. It has been revealed that the same stage of plant growth and development is first observed on the southern Armenian slopes, which is mainly due to the radiation advantage of those slopes, as well as the

mechanical composition and moisture conditions of the soil [6,10,13].

Therefore, it is extremely important to study and find out with the use of organo-mineral fertilizers and growth promoter, what changes were made during the transition of potato growth, development and phenological stages and the effect caused by them on the yield of potato tubers and bushes.

Material and method: The purpose of the work is to study and find out for the first time the effect of the equivalent amounts and dates of application of organomix organic fertilizer, growth promoting bioliquid and organomineral fertilizers obtained by the Armenian-Norwegian joint enterprise (Orwako) from household and agricultural waste with the latest biotechnological methods, on the growth of potatoes cultivated in the arid conditions of the foothills of the Republic of Artsakh, on development, transition of phenological stages and yield and compare them with the results of the influence of the ratio of mineral fertilizers applied in the region.

The studies were carried out in 2021-2022 in the Ivanyan community of the Askeran district of the Republic of Artsakh. The field experiments were carried out in post-forest brown soils, which are characteristic for the region also in the sense that the predominant part of the potato fields (86.2%) is cultivated in this soil type.

The reaction of the soil environment of the testing ground: pH varies between 6.9-7.1, humus content is 3.3 - 3.4%, with easily hydrolyzable nitrogen (N) (3.4-3.6 mg) is weakly provided, with mobile phosphorus-medium (P_2O_5 is 5.1-5.3 mg), with exchangeable potassium is good (K_2O per 100 g of soil: 34.0-36 mg) [1,6,14,15].

The field experiments were set up with 3 repetitions, the size of each version in the repetition was 20m², according to the following variants:

1. Checker (without fertilization)
2. Organomix 8t/ha one time, in sowing
3. Organomix 10t/ha one-time, in sowing
4. Organomix 5t/ha (in sowing) + $N_{30}P_{40}K_{40}$ (in sowing) + N_{30} with nutrition
5. Organomix 5t/ha in sowing + organomix 3t/ha (with nutrition) + bio-liquid 14 l/ha (nutrition)
6. Bio-liquid 14 l/ha by wetting the planting material + organomix 5 t/ha (in sowing) + organomix 3 t/ha (nutrition)
7. $N_{80}P_{80}K_{80}$ (in sowing) + N_{40} (nutrition)

Studies were conducted on the Impala potato variety, the planting rate of which was 32.4 c/ha in 2021, 33.0 c/ha in 2022 and 32,8c/ha in 2023, further processing and harvesting were carried out in accordance with the agricultural rules adopted in the region.

The full norms of organomix in the 2nd and 3rd variants were applied in the spring once, in sowing, in

the 5th, 6th versions, fractionally, in sowing and with nutrition, at the same time, in those versions, the same rate of bio-liquid (14 l/ha), in one case, nutrition was given in a foliar method, in the other case, by soaking the potato planting material three days before planting. Equivalent doses of mineral fertilizers $N_{80}P_{80}K_{80}$ were given in sowing, and N_{40} - with nutrition (version 7). In version 4, as indicated in the scheme, $N_{30}P_{40}K_{40}$ in sowing and N_{30} with nutrition were added to the soil with organomix (5t/ha). The indicated amounts of organomix and NPK were given in order to provide the content of nutrients in them equal to the (applied) amount of full norms of organomix and mineral fertilizers.

Biometric measurements and observations on plant growth, development, and transition of phenological stages in the potato experimental field were performed according to A.I. Rudenko [12] and R. S. Mkrtchyan [5,10].

The yield of potato tubers and bushes was calculated using a widespread crop accounting method, and the yield data were mathematically analyzed using dispersion analysis method, determining experimental error ($S_x, \%$) and the most significant difference (MSD 0.95 c) [8].

Results and discussion. According to the average data of three years of repetitions of field experiments, organo-mineral fertilizers individually or together and growth-promoting bio-liquid had a certain effect on potato germination, growth and development, as well as the transition of phenological stages.

During the three years, potato seedlings germinated 25-27 days after planting in the version without fertilization, after 27-28 days in the version with a full combination of mineral fertilizers, and after 23-24 days in all versions that received organic mix. In the 6th version of the field experiments, where the potato planting material was soaked with bioliquid and planting work was performed after 3 days, in that variant the potato tubers germinated 5-7 days earlier and in all years the mass germination of the planting material took place after 19-20 days. It is noteworthy that in the version sown with bioliquid-treated planting material, the potato plants grew more lushly, and there were more stems and leaves. The effect of organomix was more evident during the transition of potato phenological stages. If this effect was not pronounced during the initial stages, it was evident in the last stages (flowering and ripening) and compared to the version of the full combination of mineral fertilizers, the length of plant vegetation was reduced by 5-7 days (table 1).

During the years of field experiments, fractional application of organic mix delayed the transition of the phenological stages of potato plants more than a single application.

Table 1

The effect of applying mineral and organic fertilizers and growth stimulants on the transition of potato phenophases

N/N	Variants	In 2021				In 2022				In 2023			
		germination	from germination to cocooning	blooming	ripening	germination	Cocooning	blooming	ripening	germination	cocooning	blooming	ripening
1	Checker (without fertilization)	25/IV	25	34	64	18/IV	27	37	66	26/IV	26	36	67
2	Organomix 8t/ha one-time, in sowing	23/IV	27	35	66	15/IV	29	39	70	22/IV	27	38	69
3	Organomix 10t/ha one-time, in sowing	23/IV	27	36	67	14/IV	29	39	70	22/IV	28	38	69
4	Organomix 5t (in sowing) N ₃₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀ (in sowing)+) with N ₃₀ nutrition	24/IV	28	36	66	15/IV	28	40	69	21/IV	27	38	70
5	Organomix 5t/ha in sowing + organomix 3t/ha (with nutrition) + bio-liquid 14l/ha (nutrition)	24/IV	29	37	68	15/IV	29	40	72	22/IV	29	40	71
6	Bio-liquid 14 l/ha by wetting the planting material + organomix 5 t/ha (in sowing) + organomix 3 t/ha (nutrition)	20/IV	29	38	68	12/IV	30	40	71	19/IV	29	41	71
7	N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀ (in sowing)+ N ₄₀ (nutrition)	24/IV	27	37	71	15/IV	29	38	73	23/IV	29	29	74

Thus, if the dosages of 8 and 10 t/ha of organomix were given one-time, in sowing, the vegetation duration of potato plants was 66-70 days, and when the same dosage was given, respectively, 5 and 3 t/ha in sowing and nutrition, the vegetation of the plants was prolonged by 2-3 days and became 69-72 days.

Biometric measurements showed that single and fractional application of organomix, as well as equivalent doses of organomix and mineral fertilizers, had a beneficial effect on the height of potato plants, the number of stems, and the weight of stems and leaves (table 2). The plants of the fields fertilized with organic mix were distinguished by dark green and lush bushes,

stems with greater branching and a powerful leaf mass. In all years of the studies, the plants of the variants that received organomix were 8-14 cm higher than the plants of the variant without fertilization, and in the variant of fractional application of organomix, when the bioliquid growth promoter was added or by soaking the planting material, or by extra-root nutrition,

compared to the norm of a single application of organomix, the plant height on average was 6.0-6.1 cm higher. *Similar patterns of organomix and bioliquid effects were also observed in the results of other biometric measurements compared to the no-fertilization option and equivalent doses of mineral fertilizers.*

Table 2
Effect of application of organomineral fertilizers and growth promoter on potato above-ground mass

N/N	Variants	2021			2022			2023			Average of three years						
		Plant height, cm	Number of stems, pc	Weight g/plant	Plant height, cm	Number of stems, pc	Weight g/plant	Plant height, cm	Number of stems, pc	Weight g/plant	Plant height, cm	Number of stems, pc	Weight g/plant				
1	Checker (without fertilization)	48,0	4,2	320	120	4,4	330	130	4,4	345	50,0	4,4	345	50,2	4,3	331,7	126,7
2	Organomix 8t/ha (one-time, in sowing)	56,0	5,9	460	185	6,0	470	196	6,0	460	56,0	6,0	460	56,3	6,0	463,3	185,3
3	Organomix 10t/ha (one-time, in sowing)	56,5	6,0	470	190	6,3	484	198	6,0	468	56,8	6,0	468	57,1	6,1	474,0	192,7
4	Organomix 5t/ha (in sowing)N ₃₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀ (in sowing)+ N ₃₀ with nutrition	58,0	6,4	480	192	6,4	490	200	6,5	478	59,0	6,5	478	59,0	6,4	483,3	195,7
5	Organomix 5t/ha in sowing+organomix 3t/ha (with nutrition)+bio-liquid 14l/ha (nutrition)	60,0	6,8	482	195	6,5	496	204	7,0	484	60,0	7,0	484	60,5	6,8	487,3	199,7
6	Bioliquid 14l/ha soaking the planting material +organomix 5t/ha (in sowing)+organomix 3t/ha (nutrition)	62,0	7,2	510	225	7,4	520	216	7,2	500	63,0	7,2	500	62,7	7,3	510,0	219,7
7	N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀ (in sowing)+ N ₄₀ (nutrition)	60,0	6,3	485	194	6,4	496	200	6,5	489	59,0	6,5	489	59,3	6,4	490,0	196,7

Both one-time and fractional application of organic mix and bio-liquids had a more positive effect on potato tuber germination, plant phenophase transition and above-ground mass (size and weight) of potato plants everywhere in all years than the full combinations of mineral fertilizers applied in the zone ($N_{80}P_{80}K_{80}$ in sowing + N_{40} nutrition). The similar effect of organomix and bio-liquid is due to the fact that due to intensive fermentation, biologically active substances accumulate in the soil, which contribute to the growth and development of tubers (germination of planting material) and plants, which mineral fertilizers do not have [2,3,4,7,9]. The mentioned circumstance was expressed in the yield indicators of potato tubers (table 3). As can be seen from the data in the table, despite the three years of the studies, the effect patterns

of the tested fertilizers and growth promoters were everywhere preserved, but the level of potato yield in 2022 was higher than in 2021 and 2023. Thus, if in 2022 the potato yield in the version without fertilization was 150.0 c/ha, then in 2021 and 2023 it was 142.4 and 143.2 c/ha, respectively, or about 8 and 7 centners less. This circumstance is explained by the fact that in 2022, both the amount of atmospheric precipitation (562 mm) and the number of sunny days during tuber accumulation (38) were more favorable for the growth and development of potatoes than 2021 and 2023 which had relatively little precipitation (476 mm; 498 mm) and sunny days (with only 25 and 23 solar days during the vegetation period, especially during the tuber accumulation period [16].

Table 3

Effect of organomineral fertilizers and growth promoter on potato yield (average data of 2021-2023 repetitions)

N/N	Variants	The average yield of repetitions, by years, c/ha			The average harvest of three years, c/ha		Additional yield, c/ha
		In 2021	In 2022	In 2023	c /ha	%	
1	Checker (without fertilization)	142,4±2	150,0±3	143,2±2	144,9	-	-
2	Organomix 8t/ha (one-time, in sowing)	290,0±6	301,0±4	296,0±3	295,7	150,8	104,1
3	Organomix 10t/ha (one-time, in sowing)	296,0±7	315,±5	303,0±4	304,7	159,8	110,3
4	Organomix 5t/ha (in sowing) $N_{30}P_{40}K_{40}$ (in sowing)+ N_{30} with nutrition	300,0±4	307,0±5	302,0±3	303,0	158,1	109,1
5	Organomix 5t/ha in sowing+organomix 3t/ha (with nutrition)+bio-liquid 14l/ha (nutrition)	307,0±5	322,0±6	309,0±5	312,7	167,8	115,8
6	Bioliqid 14l/ha soaking the planting material +organomix 5t/ha (in sowing)+organomix 3t/ha (nutrition)	342,0±7	372,0±6,2	356,0±5	356,7	211,8	146,2
7	$N_{80}P_{80}K_{80}$ (in sowing)+ N_{40} (nutrition)	285,0±6	300,0±5,4	290,0±6	291,7	146,8	101,3

Sx,% 1,5 1,3 1,6

MSD 0,95 g 5,4 4,8 6,0

This fact was confirmed at the level of the Republic of Artsakh: as a result of relatively unfavorable climatic conditions in 2021 and 2023, potato yields significantly decreased compared to 2022, and this decrease amounted to 13.7 and 11.3 c/ha, respectively. Climatic conditions also had some impact on the efficiency of applied fertilizers and growth promoter: in the favorable year 2022, the efficiency of organic mix, mineral fertilizers and growth promoter was higher than in relatively unfavorable 2021 and 2023. From the data in Table 3, it is clearly seen that the yield of the tested variants in 2022 is higher by 3.8-8.8% and 1.9-4.3%, respectively, compared to similar variants in 2021 and 2023.

At the same time, it can be seen from the results of the research that the equivalent doses of organo-mineral fertilizers, compared to the version without fertilization, on an average of three years, almost

equally affected the increase in potato yield, but when in the version of fractional application of organic mix, the potato planting material was soaked with a bioliqid solution before sowing, in that version the yield increase compared to the control was the highest and was 211.8 c/ha or 146.2% even compared to the version where the bioliqid was given as foliar nutrition at the stage of potato cocooning, where the yield increase was 167.8 c/ha (115, 8%). By changing the method of bioliqid application, by soaking the seed material before planting, compared to using it in a foliar way, the difference in yield was 44.0 c/ha or 30.4% on average over three years.

This circumstance confirms that the bioliqid promoted the germination of dormant buds in the base of the potato plant material, due to which more above-ground (stems, leaves) and underground (stolons) organs appeared, resulting in increased potato yield.

According to the results of field experiments, it was proved that the fractional application of organomix and mineral fertilizers and their combined equivalent doses, compared to single application, had a more beneficial effect on potato growth, development, transition of phenological stages and increase in the amount of harvest, and as a result, if the single application of organo-mineral fertilizers provided 146, 8-150.3 c/ha crop increase (101.3-104.1%), then their fractional and combined doses - 158.1-167.8 c/ha or 109.1-115.8%.

Conclusions

Summing up the results of the field experimental work carried out during 2021-2023, we came to the following main conclusions:

1. The effect of organomix was more noticeable during the transition of potatoes to phenological stages: at the initial stages (germination, cocooning), this effect was not significant, while at later stages (flowering, ripening) it was more prominent and reduced the duration of vegetation by 5-7 days compared to the option of a full combination of mineral fertilizers.

2. Fractional application of organomix had a more favorable effect on the germination of potato tubers, the transition of phenologic stages of plants, as well as on the quantity and weight of the aboveground mass of plants (stems, leaves) than with a single application of the same norm and the introduction of complete combinations of mineral fertilizers applied in the zone (N₈₀P₈₀K₈₀ from sowing+N₄₀ with nutrition).

3. By changing the method of application of bioliquid as a growth stimulator, by soaking the seed material before planting, in comparison with the use of foliar method (with nutrition), the increase in potato yield was 44.0 c/ha or 30.4% on average over three years.

4. Fractional application of organic and mineral fertilizers and their combined equivalent doses compared to one-time application, more positively influencing potato growth, development, phenophase transition, contributed to ensuring a high yield of potatoes. Compared to the variant without fertilizing, on an average of 3 years, in the case of one-time application of organo-mineral fertilizers, 146.8-150.3 c/ha tuber crop addition or 101.3-104.1%, and their fractional and equivalent doses - 158.1-167.8 c/ha or 109.1-115.8% crop addition.

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